

EMOTIONAL MATURITY OF PROSPECTIVE SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS IN RELATION TO GENDER AND SELF-CONTROL

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation involves emotional maturity of secondary school teachers in relation to gender, self-control and family environment. Descriptive survey method was used in this research. A sample of 1200 prospective secondary school teachers of 12 different B.Ed. teacher training colleges were selected from Mandi, Kangra, Hamirpur and Bilaspur districts of Himachal Pradesh through incidental sampling technique. For data collection emotional maturity scale by Singh and Bhargva and Self-Control Scale (Self Developed Scale) were used by the investigator. The techniques of descriptive statistics, T-test and Analysis of Variance (Two Way) were used to analyze the data. The results of the study revealed that male and female prospective secondary school teachers did not differ significantly in terms of their emotional maturity and, female prospective secondary school teachers possessed higher emotional maturity as compared to male prospective secondary school teachers the prospective secondary school teachers having high, average and low level of self-control differed significantly from each other in terms of emotional maturity. Further it can be inferred that gender and self-control did not have significant difference on emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers in combined manner. Implications of the study were discussed at the end of the paper.

KEYWORDS: *Emotional Maturity, Self-Control, Prospective Secondary School Teachers.*

INTRODUCTION

In the fast-changing education industry, a teacher's role goes beyond passing on learning. Teachers are not just learning facilitators but also models who influence students' emotional and psychological growth. Of all the qualities required for good teaching, emotional maturity is one such critical element that enables teachers to perform at their best. It also helps the teacher to control his/her own emotions, respond to others' emotions, and develop a safe and stable learning environment. Prospective secondary school teachers, in particular, are at a stage in life when their professional and personal qualities are still being shaped. Their emotional maturity can be a deciding factor in how they approach issues of the classroom, relate with students and colleagues, and adjust to the challenges of the vocation. With the very interpersonal subtlety of teaching in secondary schools, where students themselves are in process of emotional and psychological transformation, a teacher's emotional maturity is all the more important. Two of the most universally accepted influential variables in emotional maturity are gender and self-control. The gender differences might impact the way individuals express and manage emotions, while regulating thoughts, feelings, and behaviors amidst temptation and impulse, self-control, is usually attributed to emotional regulation. Knowledge of how such factors function in emotional maturity among prospective teachers can be useful in guiding teacher training so that increasingly emotionally skilled and resilient

educators can be developed. This research aims to investigate the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers based on gender and self-control. By understanding these relationships, the research hopes to add to the knowledge bank in the field of educational psychology while also offering pragmatic implication for teachers' training and professional development.

REVIEWS OF RELATED LITERATURE

Maheswari (2015) observed that female prospective teachers exhibited higher levels of emotional maturity compared to males. In contrast, **Nadaf et al. (2024)** found no significant difference in emotional maturity between male and female secondary school teachers, suggesting that gender may not be a consistent predictor. **Chaplin and Aldao (2013)** also highlight that while emotional expression may vary by gender, core emotional competencies like regulation and maturity may be equally attainable across genders. **Sharma and Kumari (2016)** found a strong positive correlation between self-control and emotional maturity in B.Ed. trainees, suggesting that self-regulated individuals are more emotionally mature. Similarly, **Das and Choudhury (2020)** emphasized that high self-control supports better emotional resilience, especially in emotionally demanding professions like teaching.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to gender.
2. To study and compare the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to level of self-control.
3. To study the interactional effects between gender and self-control with regard to emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

1. There will be no significant difference in the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to gender.
2. There will be no significant difference in the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to self-control.
3. There will be no significant interaction between gender and self-control with regard to emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers.

METHODOLOGY

To fulfill the objectives of the study descriptive survey method of the research was used.

SAMPLING

A requisite sample of 1200 prospective secondary school teachers were selected from 12 B.Ed. teacher training colleges from Mandi, Kangra, Hamirpur and Bilaspur districts of Himachal Pradesh.

RESEARCH TOOL USED

For the present investigation following research tools were used for data collection.

1. Emotional Maturity Scale by Dr. Yashvir Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargva (2012).
2. Self-Control Scale: Developed by the researcher himself.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The techniques of descriptive statistics, T-test and Analysis of Variance (Two Way) were used to analyze the data. Detailed description of the results was given below:

In order to study the main and Interactional effect of gender and level of self-control on overall emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers, Analysis of Variance (2x2x3 factor design) involving two levels of gender i.e. male and female, and three levels of self-control i.e. high, average and low, was applied on mean scores of emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers. The mean overall emotional maturity scores of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to gender and level of self-control are given in table 1.

Table-1

Gender and Self-Control-Wise Scores and Means on Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers

S. No.	Gender and Level of Self-control		High	Average	Low	Total
1.	Male	Mean	106.5	98.769	92.421	99.432
		SD	23.113	23.214	23.261	23.217
		N	104	104	95	303
2.	Female	Mean	112.063	100.365	91.968	101.176
		SD	23.081	23.074	23.092	23.074
		N	266	347	284	897
3.	Total	Mean	110.013	99.511	91.936	100.735
		SD	23.081	23.074	23.092	23.074
		N	370	452	379	1200

From the meanscores of overall emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to their gender and self-control, the 'F' values were calculated. The results are given in table 2.

Table-2

Summary Table of Analysis of Variance of Emotional Maturity Scores of Prospective Secondary School Teachers

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	'F' Ratio
Gender (A)	522.093	1	522.093	1.091NS
Self-Control (B)	43604.145	2	21.802.072	45.577**
Gender and Self-Control (AXB)	510.402	2	255.201	0.533NS
Error Variance	568289.727	1188	478.358	-----
Corrected Total	638379.259	1199	-----	-----

NS Not Significant

** Significant at 0.01 level of Significance

MAIN EFFECTS

a. Gender (A): It may be seen from table 1 for the main effect of gender on emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers, the obtained value of 'F' for degree of freedom 1/1188, came out to be 1.091 which is less than the table value (6.64) even at 0.01 level of significance hence **Hypotheses No. 1** "There will be no significant difference in the Emotional Maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to Gender" was validated, therefore it may be interpreted that male and female prospective secondary school teachers did not differ significantly in terms of their emotional maturity. Further the mean score of female prospective secondary school teachers is 101.176 which is higher than the mean score of male prospective secondary school teachers i.e. 99.432. therefore, it can conclude that female prospective secondary school teachers possessed higher emotional maturity as compared to male prospective secondary school teachers. The significant difference in emotional maturity of male and female prospective secondary school teachers is shown in figure 1

Figure. 1

Difference in Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers with respect to their Gender

(b) Self-Control (B) In order to examine the main effect of emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers on self-control, the calculated value of 'F' for degree of freedom 2/1188, came out to be 45.577 which is much greater than the table value (6.64) at 0.01 level of significance, therefore the **Hypothesis No. 2** "There will be no significant difference in the Emotional Maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to Self-Control" was not retained. Thus, it may be inferred that prospective secondary school teachers having high, average and low level of self-control differed significantly from each other in terms of emotional maturity. Further it is also evident from the table 2 that mean scores of emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers having high self-control is 110.013, which is higher than the mean score of prospective secondary school teachers having average self-control (99.511) and prospective secondary teachers with low self-control (91.936).

To study the significant difference in overall emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers with respect to high, average and low level of self-control, statistical technique of T-test was applied. The results are given below:

(i) Comparison of Overall Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers having High Self-Control and Average Self-Control.

To compare the overall emotional maturity of prospective teachers possessing high and average level self-control, t-value was calculated and given table 3

Table-3

Comparison Of Overall Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers Having High Self-Control And Average Self-Control

S. No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	df	SE _D	t-value
1.	High Self-Control	370	110.013	23.671	828	1.470	5.237**
2.	Average Self-Control	451	99.511	20.305			

** Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance

From table 3 it is clear that the obtained value of 't' for the comparison of prospective secondary school teachers with high self-control and average self-control on overall emotional maturity, came out to be 5.237 for degree of freedom 828 which is significant even at 0.01 level of significance so, it may be interpreted that prospective teachers having high self-control and average self-control differ significantly with respect to their overall emotional maturity further it can be conclude from the mean scores of overall emotional maturity that prospective secondary school teachers possessing high self-control (110.013) had shown high overall emotional maturity as compare to prospective secondary school teachers having average level of self-control (99.511). Figure 2 showing the significant comparison of overall emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers having high self-control and average self-control.

Figure-2

Comparison of Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers having High Self-Control and Average Self-Control.

(ii) Comparison of Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers having High Self-Control and Low Self-Control.

For the comparison of prospective secondary school teachers possessing high and low-level self-control on overall emotional maturity, the t-value was calculated and given in table 4

Table-4

Comparison of Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers Having High Self-Control and Low Self-Control

S. No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	df	SE _D	t-value
1.	High Self-Control	370	110.013	23.671	749	1.672	10.944**
2.	Low Self-Control	379	91.936	21.953			

** Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance

It is seen from table 4 that, the obtained value of 't' for the comparison of prospective secondary school teachers with high self-control and low self-control on overall emotional maturity, came out to be 10.944 for degree of freedom 749 which is significant even at 0.01 level of significance so, it may be interpreted that prospective secondary school teachers having high and low level self-control differs significantly with respect to their overall emotional maturity, further it is clear from the mean scores that prospective secondary school teachers possessing high self-control (110.013) had shown high emotional maturity as compare to prospective teachers having low level of self-control (91.936).

The significant comparison of prospective secondary school teachers having high self-control and low self-control of overall emotional maturity is given in figure 3.

Figure-3

Comparison of Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers having High Self-Control and Low Self-Control.

(iii) Comparison of Emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers having Average Self-Control and Low Self-Control.

In order to compare the emotional maturity of prospective teachers possessing average and low-level self-control, t-value was calculated and given table 5.

Table-5

Comparison Of emotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers Having Average Self-Control And Low Self-Control

S. No.	Comparison Groups	N	Mean	S.D.	df	SE _D	t-value
1.	Average Self-Control	451	99.511	20.305	817	1.531	6.922**
2.	Low Self-Control	379	91.936	21.953			

** Significant at 0.01 Level of Significance

It is clear from table5 that the calculated value of ‘t’ for the comparison of prospective secondary school teachers with average self-control and low self-control onemotional maturity, came out to be 6.922 for degree of freedom 817 which is significant at 0.01 level of significance.therefore, it may be interpreted that prospective secondary school teachers having average self-control and low self-control differ significantly with regard toemotional maturity, further it is clear from the mean scores that prospective secondary school teachers possessing average self-control (99.511) had shown average level of emotional maturityas compare to prospective teachers having low level of self-control (91.936). The significant comparison of emotional maturityof prospective secondary school teachers having average self-control and low self-control is given in figure 4.

Figure-4

Comparison of Emotional Maturityof Prospective Secondary School Teachers having Average Self-Control and Low Self-Control.

INTERACTIONAL EFFECTS

Gender and Self-Control (AXB)In order to study the interactional effect of gender and self-control on emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers, the calculated value of F-ratio came out to be 0.533 for degree of freedom 2/1188, which is less than the table value (2.99) even at 0.05 level of significance. So, **Hypothesis No. 3 “There will be no significant interaction between Gender and Self-Control with regard toEmotional Maturity of Prospective Secondary School Teachers”** was retained, this means that gender

and self-control did not have significant difference on emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers in combined manner.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The obtained value of 'F' for degree of freedom 1/1188, came out to be 1.091 which is less than the table value (6.64) even at 0.01 level of significance therefore it may be interpreted that male and female prospective secondary school teachers did not differ significantly in terms of their emotional maturity. Further the mean score of female prospective secondary school teachers is 101.176 which is higher than the mean score of male prospective secondary school teachers i.e. 99.432.
2. The calculated 'F' value for degree of freedom 2/1188, came out to be 45.577 which is much greater than the table value (6.64) at 0.01 level of significance, therefore the it may be inferred that prospective secondary school teachers having high, average and low level of self-control differed significantly from each other in terms of emotional maturity. Further it is also evident from the table 2 that mean scores of emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers having high self-control is 110.013, which is higher than the mean score of prospective secondary school teachers having average self-control (99.511) and prospective secondary teachers with low self-control (91.936).
3. The computed value of F-ratio came out to be 0.533 for degree of freedom 2/1188, which is less than the table value (2.99) even at 0.05 level of significance. This means that gender and self-control did not have significant difference on emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers in combined manner.

IMPLICATIONS

The plan of present study was chalked out to study the emotional maturity of prospective secondary school teachers in relation to gender and self-control. After analysing the results of the study, it was revealed that there was no significant difference between male and female prospective secondary school teachers with respect to emotional maturity. However, on the basis of mean scores it was inferred that female prospective secondary school teachers somewhat possess high emotional maturity as compared to male prospective secondary school teachers. According to the finding discussions, we can say that we have to build good attitude, emotional stability and self-confidence among the young people and motivate them for good academic achievements. During the era of liberalization, privatization and globalization of education, an education system that is healthy, productive, creative and innovative is the hour of need. Education system is based on the future teachers. Teacher education is thought to be the only hope to transform the society into a good one. Teachers are those who can to make the mold the students a good citizen and emotionally matured and self-confidence to shoulder the responsibility on their shoulders for developing their nation.

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